

$(1, 2)^*$ -QUASI η -NORMAL SPACES IN BITOPOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a new class of normal space called, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space. The relationships among $(1, 2)^*$ -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal, mildly $(1, 2)^*$ -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi α -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -mildly α -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -normal and mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal spaces are investigated. Moreover, we introduce some closed functions such as $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed. Utilizing $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets and some functions, we obtain some characterizations and preservation theorems for $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces.

KEYWORDS: $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets; $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -continuous, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -continuous functions; $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The study of bitopological space was first initiated by Kelly [7] in 1963. By using the topological notions, namely, semi-open, α -open and pre-open sets, many new bitopological sets are defined and studied by many topologists. In 1990, Lal and Rahman [13] studied quasi normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their properties. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [4] further studied quasi normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2004, Ravi and Thivagar [16] studied the concept of stronger form of $(1, 2)^*$ -quotient mapping in bitopological spaces and also introduced the concepts of $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open and $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open sets. In 2010, Arockiarani [2] introduced $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \alpha$ -closed sets in bitopological spaces and studied some basic properties of $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \alpha$ -closed sets. In 2010, K. Kayathri et al. [6] introduced and studied a new class of sets called regular $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed sets and used it to obtain a new class of functions called $(1, 2)^*$ - rg -continuous and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - rg -closed functions in bitopological spaces and also obtained characterizations and preservation theorems for mildly $(1, 2)^*$ -normal spaces. In 2011, Arockiarani [3] introduced $(1, 2)^*$ - α -normal spaces in bitopological spaces and studied some basic properties. In 2018, H. Kumar [8] introduced and studied some weaker forms of quasi normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2022, H. Kumar [9] introduced the concept of $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -neighbourhood and; studied their properties. H. Kumar [10] introduced the concept of $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -closed sets and studied some basic properties of $(1, 2)^*$ - $g \eta$ -closed sets. H. Kumar [11] introduced and studied some new functions called almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -continuous, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g \eta$ -continuous, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $rg \eta$ -continuous, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - $g \eta$ -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - $rg \eta$ -closed, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $rg \eta$ -closed functions in bitopological spaces and obtained some characterizations and preservation theorems for mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal spaces. Recently, H. Kumar [12] introduced and studied $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets in bitopological spaces and obtained their properties.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout the paper $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, (Y, σ_1, σ_2) and (Z, \wp_1, \wp_2) (or simply X, Y and Z) denote bitopological spaces.

Definition 2.1. Let S be a subset of X . Then S is said to be $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open [16] if $S = A \cup B$ where $A \in \mathfrak{T}_1$ and $B \in \mathfrak{T}_2$. The complement of a $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed.

Definition 2.2 [16]. Let S be a subset of X . Then

(i) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closure of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S)$, is defined as $\cap \{F : S \subset F \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-closed}\}$; (ii) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -interior of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S)$, is defined as $\cup \{F : F \subset S \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open}\}$.

Note 2.3 [16]. Notice that $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets need not necessarily form a topology.

Definition 2.4. A subset A of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called

- (i) **regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open** [16] if $A = \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$.
- (ii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - π -open** [2] if A is the finite union of $(1, 2)^*$ -regular-open sets.
- (iii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -open** [9] if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)) \cup \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)))$.

The complement of a regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open) set is called **regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed**).

The **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -closure** of a subset A of X is denoted by **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A)**, defined as the intersection of all $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets containing A . The **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -interior** of S , denoted by **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -int(S)**, is defined as $\cup \{F : F \subset S \text{ and } F \text{ is } (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open}\}$.

The family of all regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open (resp. regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed) sets in X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*\text{-RO}(X)$ (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-RC}(X)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-O}(X)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-C}(X)$).

Remark 2.5. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets [12]:

$$\text{regular } (1, 2)^*\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi\text{-open} \Rightarrow \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible.

Definition 2.6. A subset A of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called

- (i) **$(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -closed** (briefly **$(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed**) [10] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open in X .
- (ii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - π generalized η -closed** (briefly **$(1, 2)^*$ - π g η -closed**) [12] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ -open in X .

The complement of a $(1, 2)^*\text{-g}\eta$ -closed (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -closed) set is called **$(1, 2)^*\text{-g}\eta$ -open** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -open**).

We denote the set of all $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -closed (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -open) sets in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ by $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -C(X) (resp. π g η -O(X)).

Theorem 2.7. [12]. A set A is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ g η -open if and only if the following condition holds:

$$F \subset (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(A) \text{ whenever } F \text{ is } (1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi\text{-closed and } F \subset A.$$

3. $(1, 2)^*$ -QUASI η -NORMAL SPACES IN BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

In this section, we introduce $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces in bitopological spaces and study some basic properties of $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces.

Definition 3.1. A space X is said to be **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal** [11] (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -normal** [3]) if for every pair of disjoint $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open (resp. $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

Definition 3.2. A space X is said to be **$(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ -quasi normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi α -normal** [2]) if for every pair of disjoint $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\pi$ -closed H, K of X , there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open (resp. $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

Definition 3.3. A space X is said to be **mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal** [11] (resp. **mildly $(1, 2)^*$ -normal** [6] **mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - α -normal**) if for every pair of disjoint $H, K \in (1, 2)^*\text{-RC}(X)$, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open (resp. $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

Remark 3.4. From the definitions stated above, we obtain the following diagram.

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following example:

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then the pair of disjoint regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed sets $H = \{a\}$ and $K = \{c, d\}$, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets $U = \{a\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Hence $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal but not mildly $(1, 2)^*$ -normal, since $V = \{c, d\}$ is not $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}\}$. Then the pair of disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets $H = \phi$ and $K = \{b\}$, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets $U = \{a\}$ and $V = \{b, c\}$ such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Hence $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal but it is neither $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi normal nor $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi α -normal, since $V = \{b, c\}$ is neither $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open nor $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the pair of disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets $H = \phi$ and $K = \{c\}$, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets $U = \{b\}$ and $V = \{a, c\}$ such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Hence $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal but it is neither $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi normal nor $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi α -normal, since $V = \{b, c\}$ is neither $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open nor $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set.

Theorem 3.8. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.
- For every pair of $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open subsets U and V of X whose union is X , there exist $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.
- For any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed set A and every π -open set B in X such that $A \subset B$, there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset B$.
- For every pair of disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) \cap $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(V) = ϕ .

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d) and (d) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let U and V be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open subsets of a $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space X such that $U \cup V = X$. Then, $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed subsets of X . By $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normality of X , there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X - U \subset U_1$ and $X - V \subset V_1$. Let $G = X - U_1$ and $H = X - V_1$. Then, G and H are $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed subsets of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be a $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed and B is a $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open subsets of X such that $A \subset B$. Then, $X - A$ and B are $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open subsets of X such that $(X - A) \cup B = X$. Then, by part (b), there exist $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets G and H of X such that $G \subset (X - A)$, $H \subset B$ and $G \cup H = X$. Then, $A \subset (X - G)$, $(X - B) \subset (X - H)$ and $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = \phi$. Let $U = X - G$ and $V = (X - H)$. Then U and V are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets such that $A \subset U \subset X - V \subset B$. Since $X - V$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, then we have $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset (X - V)$. Thus, $A \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset B$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let A and B be any disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed subset of X . Then $A \subset X - B$, where $X - B$ is π -open. By the part (c), there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset X - B$. Let $V = X - (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U). Then, V is a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open subset of X . Thus, we obtain $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) \cap $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(V) = ϕ .

(d) \Rightarrow (a). It is obvious.

The following result is useful for giving some other characterization of $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces.

Theorem 3.9. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.
- (b) For any disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (c) For any disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (d) For any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed set H and any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open set V containing H , there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset V$.
- (e) For any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed set H and any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open set V containing H , there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset V$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d), (d) \Rightarrow (e) and (e) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let X be $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space. Let H, K be disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets U, V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since every $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open, so U and V are $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let H, K be two disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open, so U and V are $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let H be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed set and V be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open sets U and W such that $H \subset U$ and $X - V \subset W$. By **Theorem 2.7**, we get $X - V \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -int(W) and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\cap (1, 2)^*$ - η -int(W) = ϕ . Hence $H \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset X - (1, 2)^*$ - η -int(W) $\subset V$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Let H be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed set and V be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset V$. Since, every $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open, there exists $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subset U \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(U) $\subset V$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let H, K be any two disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of X . Then $H \subset X - K$ and $X - K$ is π -open. By assumption, there exists $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open set G of X such that $H \subset G \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(G) $\subset X - K$. Put $U = (1, 2)^*$ - η -int(G), $V = X - (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(G). Then U and V are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

4. PRESERVATION THEOREMS

In this section, we shall recall the definitions of some functions used in the sequel. Further we introduce some $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed functions in bitopological spaces.

Definition 4.1. A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (i) **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -continuous** [11] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed in X for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of Y ;
- (ii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -continuous** [12] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of Y ;
- (iii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous** [2] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed in X for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of Y ;

Definition 4.2. A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (i) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ -continuous** [6] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -open in X for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RO(Y);
- (ii) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous** [2] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed in X for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(Y);
- (iii) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -continuous** [12] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(Y);

Definition 4.3. A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (i) **regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed** [6] if $f(F)$ is regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed in Y for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of X ;
- (ii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed** [11] if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed in Y for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of X ;
- (iii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed** [11] if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed in Y for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of X ;
- (iv) **$(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed** if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y for every $\mathfrak{S}_{1,2}$ -closed set F of X .

Definition 4.4. A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (i) **$(1, 2)^*$ -rc-preserving** [6] if $f(F)$ is regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed in Y for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(X);
- (ii) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed** [11] if $f(F)$ is $\psi_{1,2}$ -closed in Y for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(X);

- (iii) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed [11]** if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed in Y for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(X);
 (iv) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed [11]** if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed in Y for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(X);
 (v) **almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed** if $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y for every $F \in (1, 2)^*$ -RC(X);

Remark 4.5. From the definitions stated above, we obtain the following diagram.

The following examples enable us to realize that none of the implications in the above diagram is reversible.

Example 4.6. Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}\}$, $\psi_1 = \{\phi, Y, \{a, b\}\}$ and $\psi_2 = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $f(a) = b$; $f(b) = a$; $f(c) = c$. Clearly f is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed as well as almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed. It is also almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed. But it is neither $(1, 2)^*$ -closed nor almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed. It is neither $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed nor almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed.

Example 4.7. Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}\}$, $\psi_1 = \{\phi, Y, \{a, b\}\}$ and $\psi_2 = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $f(a) = b$, $f(b) = c$, $f(c) = a$. But it is neither $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed nor almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed. It is neither $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed nor almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed.

Example 4.8. Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{a, c\}\}$, $\psi_1 = \{\phi, Y, \{a, b\}\}$ and $\psi_2 = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $f(a) = b$; $f(b) = a$; $f(c) = c$. Clearly f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed as well as almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed, but it is not $(1, 2)^*$ -closed. It is also almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed

Example 4.9. Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}\}$, $\psi_1 = \{\phi, Y, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}\}$ and $\psi_2 = \{\phi, Y, \{a, b\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $f(a) = c$, $f(b) = b$, $f(c) = a$. Clearly f is $(1, 2)^*$ -closed as well as almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed. It is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed as well as almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed. But it is neither regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed nor $(1, 2)^*$ -rc-preserving.

Example 4.10. Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}\}$, $\psi_1 = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $\psi_2 = \{\phi, Y, \{c\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $f(a) = a$; $f(b) = c$; $f(c) = b$. Clearly f is $(1, 2)^*$ -rc-preserving as well as almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed.

Theorem 4.11. If $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous and $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed function, then $f(A)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y for every $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed set of X and V be any $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open set of Y containing $f(A)$. Since f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - π -open in X and $A \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, we have $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) $\subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f((1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A)) $\subset V$. Since f is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed, $f((1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A)) is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y and hence we obtain $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl($f(A)$) $\subset (1, 2)^*$ - η -cl($f((1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A))) $\subset V$. Hence $f(A)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y .

Theorem 4.12. A surjection $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed if and only if for each subset S of Y and each $U \in (1, 2)^*$ -RO(X) containing $f^{-1}(S)$, there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open set V of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed. Let S be a subset of Y and $U \in (1, 2)^*$ -RO(X) containing $f^{-1}(S)$. If $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open set of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Sufficiency. Let F be any regular $(1, 2)^*$ -closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \subset (X - F)$ and $(X - F) \in (1, 2)^*$ -RO(X). There exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset (X - F)$. Therefore, we have $f(F) \supset (Y - V)$ and $F \subset X - f^{-1}(V) \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence we obtain $f(F) = Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed in Y , which shows that f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

Theorem 4.13. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi\eta$ -continuous, $(1, 2)^*$ -rc-preserving injection and Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal then X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of X . Since f is a $(1, 2)^*$ -rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of Y . Since Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$ and $f(B) \subset V$.

Now if $G = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(U))$ and $H = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(V))$. Then G and H are regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open sets such that $f(A) \subset G$ and $f(B) \subset H$. Since f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi\eta$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi\eta$ -open sets containing A and B which shows that X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

Theorem 4.14. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed surjection and X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space then Y is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Let $G = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(U))$ and $H = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. Now, we set $K = Y - f(X - G)$ and $L = Y - f(X - H)$. Then K and L are $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, K and L are disjoint. Since K and L are $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open and we obtain $A \subset (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(K)$, $B \subset (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(L)$ and $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(K) \cap (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(L) = \phi$. Therefore, Y is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal.

Theorem 4.15. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi\eta$ -closed surjection. If X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space then Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of Y . Since f is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - π -continuous, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - π -closed sets of X . Since X is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal, there exist disjoint $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Put $G = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(U))$ and $H = (1, 2)^*\text{-int}((1, 2)^*\text{-cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. By **Theorem 4.12**, there exist $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets K and L of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L by **Theorem 2.7**, $A \subset (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(K)$, $B \subset (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(L)$ and $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(K) \cap (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-int}(L) = \phi$. Therefore, Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

Corollary 4.16. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $(1, 2)^*$ -continuous and almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed surjection and X is a $(1, 2)^*$ -normal space, then Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

Proof. Since every almost $(1, 2)^*$ -closed function is almost $(1, 2)^*$ - $\pi\eta$ -closed by **Theorem 4.15**, Y is $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduce a new class of normal space called, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal space. The relationships among $(1, 2)^*$ -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal, mildly $(1, 2)^*$ -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi α -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ -mildly α -normal, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -normal and mildly $(1, 2)^*$ - η -normal spaces are investigated. Moreover, we introduce some functions such as $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η - π -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\pi\eta$ -closed, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η - π -closed and almost $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\pi\eta$ -closed. Utilizing $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets and some functions, we obtain some characterizations and preservation theorems for $(1, 2)^*$ -quasi η -normal spaces. This idea can be extended to ordered topological, ordered bitopological and fuzzy topological spaces etc.

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